

THE DIFFICULTIES OF TRANSLATING PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE MODERN ENGLISH-LANGUAGE PRESS

To'ychiyeva Dilafruz

student, Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10649296>

As it is clear, phraseological units play very important role in every area and developed different types of phraseological units: artistic phraseological units, journalistic phraseological units, colloquial phraseological units, official-business phraseological units, scientific phraseological units. The rapid development of phraseology as a linguistic discipline in recent years has been characterized by a gradual differentiation of the concepts of the subject of research and the methodology of its study, as well as the inclusion in the sphere of scientific research of all new problems and aspects that refer to the established theoretical foundations of phraseology in linguistics.

The study of phraseological units is of particular interest. The definition of phraseological units is unambiguous, narrowly structured, stylistically directed and limited to a certain sphere of use. If this is a euphemism, a book expression, a limited expression, or a vulgarism, then they have a certain contextual configuration corresponding to this content.

Currently, the English-language press occupies a special position in the global information space. The volume of texts in English-language media significantly exceeds the same volume in other languages. The topic of publications in the English press covers not only the internal problems of the country, but also the sphere of foreign relations and therefore is constantly in close contact with other languages. This contributes to the active interaction of words and phrases, the emergence and spread of new phraseological units.

Various expressive and pictorial means are used on the pages of English-language media, among which phraseological units or phraseological units occupy a special place. The phraseological fund of the modern English language is rich and diverse, and each part of its research deserves special attention.

The study of the phraseological units used in the texts of the modern English-language press is of particular importance, since the use of phraseological units adds a vivid emotional coloring to these texts. Thanks to phraseological units, the aesthetic aspect of the language is enhanced. The place and role of the press, which has been tested in many ways by the traditional cultural and information form, cannot be understood at present without

analyzing the impact it has on the way of thinking and social behavior of readers who are actively involved in the communication process as subjects.

The study of phraseological units as linguistic units that most clearly express the national peculiarities of the culture of a native-speaking people seems important in connection with the desire for an adequate perception of the mentality of representatives of this people against the background of developing ties in various spheres of human activity.

The processes currently taking place in the English language are quite active, new phenomena arise and develop rapidly. Such active processes include the use of various stylistic techniques in the language of the media. At the same time, it is not only a linguistic, but also a sociological, cultural phenomenon that expresses the processes taking place in society and in the mind of a native speaker. Due to their relevance, the media are a good source of materials for the analysis of modern English speech, as they reflect it directly, in the very process of development.

The translation of the phraseological units causes significant difficulties. The large number of mistakes made by translators when transmitting phraseological units indicates that the problem is quite acute. Therefore, a lot of attention is paid to the translation of phraseological units in linguistic research. The problems associated with this are treated in different ways. Depending on the situation, a different approach, a different translation strategy, and different translation solutions are required.

It is clear that different methods may be appropriate in different situations. But the main focus here lies on the personality of the translator himself. He must feel like a part of the culture in which a particular text is written, must get used to it, create the only possible and at the same time unique translation option. To do this, he needs to include in his work the totality of the realities of someone else's culture, and present someone else's thoughts clearly and freshly.

References:

1. Alyokhina A.I. Phraseological unit and word. – Minsk, 1991.
2. Anichkov I.E. Works on linguistics. Russian phraseology, its development and sources. – L.: Nauka, 1990.
3. Bruskina T. L., Shitova L.F. Brief Russian-English. - St. Petersburg: Nauka, 1997.
4. Babkin A.M. Russian phraseology, its development and sources. - L.: Nauka, 1990.
4. Bruskina T. L., Shitova L.F. Brief Russian-English phraseological dictionary. — St. Petersburg: Lan, 1999.
5. Gayrin S. G. Phraseology of the modern Russian language. — Perm, 1974.

SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

International scientific-online conference

6. Nizhneva N.N., Nizhneva-Ksenofontova N.L. Professional training of translators/ Research, Modern communication studies. No. 2, 2013. – pp. 45-50.

